

Wireless Charging for Electrical Vehicles using Solar and Wind

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Abstract— A Hybrid Solar-Wind powered charging station is planned to deliver electricity for the Electric Vehicles. The new hybrid vehicle charging station brings with it completely different sources like PV systems, wind systems, AC delivered, batteries area unit used as a main energy storage system, kind DC little grid for always energy carry out. This Paper explains relative accomplishment Hybrid Solar-Wind powered charging station. In the world of electrical technology Electric vehicles play an essential role in energy saving and emission reduction of harmful greenhouse gases. The rising of energy cost, the mass electrification of everyday life, and global warming are the major drivers that will be determine the speed at which such transformations will happen. Nevertheless of how quickly various utilities acceptance clever grid concepts, technologies, and systems, they all agree on the inevitability of this huge change. Charging station, as one of the most important feature of Electric Vehicle industry, must be able to accommodate the fast development of electric vehicles.

Keywords— Solar panel, Wind Turbine, Arduino Nano, Bluetooth Module, Lead Acid Battery, Atmel 89C2051 Micro controller

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless charging uses an electromagnetic field to transfer energy between two objects. This is usually done with a charging station. Energy is sent through an inductive coupling to an electrical device, which can then use that energy to charge batteries or run the device[1].

Wireless chargers uses an induction coil to create an alternating Electro Magnetic Field from within a charging base and a second induction coil in the portable device takes power from the electromagnetic field and converts it back into electric current to charge the battery. The two induction coils in proximity combine to form an electrical transformer. Greater distances between sender and receiver coils can be achieved when the inductive charging system uses resonant inductive coupling[2]. This project falls under the subject of wireless energy, which creates an EMF by which energy will be transferred from one coil to another coil without any conducting wires. The power transmitting coil as well as power receiving coil both must be arranged parallel to each other at a certain distance[3]. Depending up on the power source, power transmitting range can be increased to a maximum distance of 4 to 5 centimeters. This kind of free wireless energy sources can be utilized without wiring. Since it is a prototype module, here low power transmitter is designed and hence the range will be less than 3.5 to 4 centimeters[4].

A. Literature Review

Peter K Joseph and D Elangovan Introduced Renewable Energy Powered Wireless Power Transmission Techniques for Light Electric Vehicle Charging Applications. This pattern is achieved through the optimum selection and design of compensator, wireless transformer and the battery packs. As the conservation of energy and exploration of renewable energy resources became a common aspect in every novel technological entities, solar power and fuel cells made its debut to wireless charging[1].

K Nethra, BansilalBairwa, SaiKiran GS and TejasGowda KB Introduced the Modeling and Simulation of Wireless Electric Vehicle Charging using Solar and Wind Energy for the fuel existing vehicles produce air,

noise pollution and it produces many other effects. Due to these impacts, conventional fuel for vehicles is changing to battery. The battery bank in charging station will be charged from solar and wind based on availability[2].

Aganti Mahesh Proposed an Inductive Wireless Power Transfer charging for Electric Vehicles by considering a future scenario in which a driverless EV needs an automatic charging system without human intervention. In this regard, there is a requirement for a fully automatable, fast, safe, cost-effective, and reliable charging infrastructure that provides a profitable business model and fast adoption in the electrified transportation systems[3].

Zicheng Bi, Tianze Kan, Chunting Chris Mi, Zhengming Zhao and Gregory AKeoleian Introduced Wireless Power Transfer for Electric Vehicles: Prospects to enhance Sustainable Mobility. The challenges and opportunities in terms of technology and sustainability performance have been enumerated and discussed. Progress in technology has led to improved system performance. Stationary wireless charging systems have comparable system performance to conductive charging systems, and dynamic wireless charging systems are on the path to achieve the charging of vehicles in motion[4].

I. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram of Wireless Charging for Electrical Vehicles using Solar and Wind is indicated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Block diagram

The major part of this project is Solar Panel and the Wind Turbine. The Solar panel will convert the Light energy into Electrical Energy and store that energy in battery at transmission side and the Wind turbine will convert the Kinetic energy into Electrical energy and store that energy in battery of transmission side. This will make the continuous Power supply to charge the electrical vehicles without any discontinuity in charging .

A. Arduino Nano

Arduino Nano plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety of the wireless power transmission system. It incorporates various safety features, such as overcurrent protection and voltage regulation, to prevent

damage to the electric vehicle or the power transmission components. Arduino NANO implements protocols for wireless communication between the power transmitter and the receiver in the electric vehicle, ensuring efficient power transfer. The Fig. 2 shows Arduino Nano.

Fig. 2 Arduino Nano

B. Solar panel

Solar panel can deliver a maximum power of 800 milli amps at 12V under the bright Sun. The entire power transmitting circuit power consumption from the panel is detected as 500 milliamps. This is the maximum power consumption, means when the secondary coil is kept very close to the primary coil, maximum power will be transmitted. The Fig. 3 shows the type of Solar panel.

Fig. 3 Solar panel (Polycrystalline)

C. Bluetooth Module

The Bluetooth wireless technology is set to revolutionize the way people perceive digital devices in our homes and office environment. The Fig. 4 shows the Bluetooth Module.

Fig. 4 Bluetooth Module

D. Wind Turbine

Wind turbine plays a critical role in generating electrical power. Wind turbine works by capturing the kinetic energy of the wind and converting it into mechanical energy through the rotation of blades. This mechanical energy is then converted into electrical energy using a generator. The electricity generated by the wind turbines can be used directly to power the wireless power transmission system or stored in batteries for later use. The Fig. 5 shows the Wind Turbine.

Fig. 5 Wind Turbine

E. Lead Acid Battery

Lead Acid Battery serves as a vital component for storing and delivering electrical energy to the vehicle. While newer battery technologies like lithium-ion are becoming more popular, lead-acid batteries are still widely used due to their reliability, low cost, and familiarity in many applications. The Fig. 6 shows the Wind Turbine.

Fig. 6 Lead Acid Battery

F. Atmel 89C2051 Microcontroller

ATMEL 89C2051-24 PU, 2K Bytes, 20 pin IC. AT89C2051 is a low-voltage, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcomputer with 2K bytes of Flash Programmable and Erasable Read Only Memory (PEROM). The device is manufactured using Atmel's high-density non-volatile memory technology and is compatible with the industry-standard MCS-51 instruction set. By combining a versatile 8-bit CPU with

Flash on a monolithic chip, The Atmel AT89C2051 is a powerful microcomputer which provides a highly-flexible and cost-effective solution to many embedded control applications. The Fig. 7 shows the Atmel 89C2051 Microcontroller.

Fig. 7 Atmel 89C2051 Microcontroller

G. LCD Display

LCD display serves as a critical interface between the system and the user. It provides valuable information about the system's operation, performance, and status, enhancing the user's understanding and control over the system. One of the primary functions of the LCD display is to provide real-time data on the power generation from the solar panels and wind turbines. The Fig. 8 shows the LCD Display which shows the value of voltage.

Fig. 8 LCD Display

II. HARDWARE MODULE

Construction

The construction typically includes solar panels and wind turbines to harness renewable energy, a power conditioning unit, a wireless power transmitter, and a wireless power receiver installed in the EV. Solar panels convert sunlight into electricity, while wind turbines convert wind energy into mechanical power, which is then converted into electricity. The wireless power transmitter consists of a coil that generates a magnetic field when supplied with electricity.

Fig. 9 Hardware Module Top view

The front view of the Hardware Module is shown in fig below:

Fig. 10 Hardware Module Front view

Wireless charging is an efficient way for the transmission of electric power from one point to another through air without the use of wire. By using Wireless Energy, power can be transmitted using inductive coupling for short range resonant induction for mid-range. The working principle is based on magnetic resonance coupling or inductive coupling. The transmitter coil creates a magnetic field, which is picked up by the receiver coil in the EV. This induces a current in the receiver coil, which is then used to charge the EV's battery.

IV. TESTING AND RESULTS

A. Electric vehicle controlled by Bluetooth

Electric Vehicle control is designed using Bluetooth technology, so the user can control its movement through the android mobile. This allows for remote monitoring and control of the vehicle's charging and operational parameters. The Bluetooth module in the Electric Vehicle communicates with a mobile device or a central control unit, enabling the user to check the charging status, battery level, and other relevant information. Additionally, it allows for the remote activation of charging and other functions, enhancing the user's convenience and control over the vehicle as shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 Vehicle controlled by Bluetooth

B. Battery charge using solar indicating through LED

Here, we are testing this under Two Conditions:

- i) **During Normal Condition:** The Solar Panel is charging the Battery Normally.
- ii) **Under Bright Sun:** Under this condition, i.e., when the intensity of light is heavy during Sunny conditions than, the Solar panel is Converting the maximum amount of light energy into Electrical Energy and storing it in Battery. This is indicating through the LED as shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Battery charge using solar

C. Battery charge using Wind indicating through LED

Wind turbine converts the kinetic energy of the wind into electrical energy through a generator. The battery stores the electrical energy generated by the wind turbine for later use. When the wind turbine is actively generating electricity and charging the battery, the LED indicator illuminates, indicating that wind energy is being utilized to power the system as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Battery charge using Wind

D. Showing Voltage drop on LCD by manually operating Relay

Here, Relay is activated when the voltage reaches to the cut-off voltage. So, here the voltage level does not reach the cut-off value so the relay is not activated. But, we are activating it manually. So, that the Voltage is dropped down compared to the before one as shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 Voltage level before and after of Activation of Relay

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this paper we are focused on Wireless Charging for EVs utilizing Solar and Wind Energy stands as a promising venture toward Sustainable and Efficient Transportation solutions. By integrating Renewable energy sources into the EV charging infrastructure. Wireless charging for Electric Vehicles (EVs) using solar and wind energy represents a significant step towards sustainable transportation. This technology combines the benefits of renewable energy sources with the convenience and efficiency of wireless power transfer, offering a promising solution for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on fossil fuels. This project can be further enhanced with the efficiency of WPT systems, reducing energy losses during transfer and optimizing energy conversion from solar and wind sources. This could lead to more effective utilization of Renewable energy for EV charging. Increasing the effective range and charging speeds of wireless systems, making them more comparable to wired charging methods. Advancements in Resonant and Inductive charging Technologies hold potential for faster and more extended range wireless charging capabilities.

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